

e-IRG Statement on the Draft Council Conclusions on the Pact for Research and Innovation for Europe

Statement on the new ERA by the e-Infrastructure Reflection Group

The e-Infrastructure Reflection Group (e-IRG) as an intergovernmental policy advisory body in the e-Infrastructure area composed of national delegates nominated by their research-related ministries operational since almost 20 years is taking initiative,

the e-IRG recognises

that the New ERA is of fundamental relevance for the whole of Europe, in terms of innovation, competitiveness and sovereignty.

the e-IRG overlooks

the whole e-Infrastructure spectrum, from networking and computing to data and related services, covering not only short-term but also longer-term aspects and thus

the e-IRG reaffirms

that the ERA priority areas addressed through the Pact for Research and Innovation for Europe are the main challenges of the presently instauration of the new ERA.

the e-IRG reiterates

- the need for coordination among e-Infrastructures and Research Infrastructures and welcomes that the draft Council Conclusions underline this necessity;
- the need for establishing and safeguarding the interoperability of national, transnational and European infrastructures for all those active in the ERA.

Represented through its Chair and its Delegates

the e-IRG declares

1. to **work together** in the ERA building process supporting to maximise the potential of the new ERA:
2. Gathering and offering **competences in e-Infrastructures**
3. Ensuring **access to e-Infrastructures**
4. Facilitating **transnational access** to services and open data through resilient infrastructures
5. **Enhancing the rapid reconfigurability** of services and infrastructures
6. Strengthening awareness towards an **inclusive and fair gender environment** in connection with research infrastructures

for the benefit and wellbeing of European citizens, their society and the European economy.

On behalf of the members of the e-IRG, the Chair
Date

